

SITUATIONAL CENTERS IN THE FIELD OF NATIONAL SECURITY AND DEFENSE OF UKRAINE

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***Abstract.** The topic of national security is relevant and demanding, especially in our country, when there is a war, combining multi-vector directions of society and a set of measures to ensure national interests: military, political, security, economic, social, legal, educational, health, etc., which are aimed at improving the standard of living of people and peaceful existence. Based on the subjects of national security, the following can be distinguished: human and public security, state security and socio-economic, environmental and technogenic and energy, information and cyber security. It is for analytical and information security that the newly created units – situational centers are responsible, having important tasks and methods of implementation, determining the main strategy of independence and sovereignty, originality and Ukrainian identity, unity and stability, democracy and security, comprehensive development of society and the national idea, taking into account socio-economic capabilities and combat readiness and combat capability of our state. The situation center is a modern tool of any organization, often a state one, which is responsible for the information and analytical component of management, the functioning of which consists of analysis, notification, monitoring of the state of the object, processing and generalization of information, forecasting and*

mathematical and computational modeling of the further development of the situation, setting goals and objectives of the final result, interaction and coordination with external and internal sectors of the process, security and defense, using all means and forces of directing, informing and updating data for management, analyzing, processing and evaluating performance and reporting. Ukraine is going through difficult times, there is a brutal war going on in the country, every Ukrainian is fighting for our state by all possible means. The work of situational centers differs in the methodology of managerial decision-making during daily functioning and is of a non-military nature (state authorities and local self-government bodies are involved, security and defense sectors), and it is a completely different matter when there is a war in the country (involvement of defense forces, operational military groups, etc.).

Keywords: *national security, situational centers, situational modeling of the system, Armed Forces of Ukraine, information and analytical center.*

The novelty of the topic and the relevance of scientific solutions. The study covers the topic of situational centers, their role and tasks at the present stage of the country's development under martial law. The definition of the concept of "situation center", classification features, tasks, modeling system and levels of this direction are the impetus for further study and research of the new concept. By setting specific tasks and goals of situational centers, you clearly understand the need and relevance of the topic, the need for development both in the scientific field and in the practical field.

Objective. Taking into account the relevance of the topic, and the need to improve the qualification level of specialists in the field of national security and public administration, applying and combining targeted specialized knowledge with practical application to solve complex professional problems and make effective decisions for the stability and prosperity of our state.

Research methodology. On the basis of the purpose and objectives of the study, a comprehensive analysis of methods and forms was used and applied, which provided wide methodological opportunities that reveal and detail the topic in a more specific and scientifically analyzed way. The definition of the institutional and regulatory basis of the concept of "situational centers", the allocation by classification criteria on the basis of the analytical method, the methodology of substantiation and grouping of scientific and legislative material were used in the unification of the tasks of the situational centers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the Ministry of Defense.

Statement of the main material.

1. Situation center is a purposeful set of actions. The national security of the country is the main strategy of our state. This is especially true when looking at the difficult present that our Ukraine is experiencing. War is the intersection of life before and after, it is broken destinies and crippled lives. "National security is the protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, democratic constitutional order and other national interests of Ukraine from real and potential threats." [1]. The topic of national security arises from the emergence of state territorial integrity, is constantly evolving and acquiring new trends that correspond to modernity. National security is responsible for the protection of the state from threats, starting with its citizens (protection of constitutional rights and freedoms), protection of society (national values: moral and ethical, spiritual, historical and cultural, economic and material, intellectual and informational, preservation and enrichment of natural resources), ending with the protection of the state level (sovereignty, sustainable development, territorial integrity).

Our country is doing everything possible to merge Ukrainians with the European community. The topic of situational centers is relevant. The necessary communication, continuous communication for timely decisions between all

authorities, society, business, collection and reproduction of information, etc., bring rationality and efficiency to the work of the state.

The Main First Situation Center was established at the National Security and Defense Council of Ukraine in 2015, and since then, development trends, influence in all spheres of the country's life have been expanding and improving every year. A large amount of information, the development of the latest means of communication give hope for the use of this complex process for the benefit of Ukraine.

The fight against the aggressor and the prevention of the spread of fake information also contributes to our victory.

One of the effective and productive levers for the possibility of implementing situational approaches in management are situational centers, which, on the basis of complex systematic and sequential actions and analysis, make it possible to make the right rational decisions and identify effective tools that will contribute to development in the future.

"Situational centers are tools for making operational management decisions. They provide information and analytics on the activities of public authorities in the areas of national security and defense. It is also the primary source of up-to-date information on important national events. Situational centers make it possible to respond quickly to crisis situations in the state. In particular, public bodies can effectively perform the tasks assigned to them. The legal regulation will ensure the reliable functioning of the situational centers of the state in peacetime, as well as in a special period, in particular in conditions of martial law or a state of emergency and during crisis situations that threaten the national security of Ukraine." [2].

Table 1. Definition of the Concept of "Situational Centers" in the Modern Scientific Understanding

№	Author	Definition
1	Ministry of Defense of Ukraine	The situation center is a modern form of organization of analytical activities, which is based on the synthesis of

		information and communication technologies, means of accumulation and presentation of information.[3].
2	Prystaiko V.V.	SC means not only a specially equipped room, but also the appropriate information, telecommunication, software and methodological means that ensure the process of delivery, aggregation of information in order to develop an appropriate management decision.[4].
3	Gladun Yu.Ya., Lipentsev A.V	SCs form an information space for effective monitoring, forecasting, decision-making and control of their implementation, which allows to implement a new format of management in conditions of severe shortage of time and resources, to assess possible strategic, political, economic, social, environmental risks that may arise in different scenarios of management situations. [5].

Source: created by the author based on the analysis of scientific literature. [3-5].

Situation center is a purposeful set of actions aimed at solving situational management problems, using the latest means of data transmission in the interaction of all process bodies.

2. Tasks of situational centers. The main task set by the situation center is to build a visual image of a particular situation that takes place in the subject area, which requires managerial decision-making, on the basis of the preparation of proposals and analytical and information materials. The center includes: - operational staff (clear and mobile problem solving); - competence and information staff (solving complex and complex-dynamic solutions); - situational and managerial staff (innovation, information and computing equipment). Situational centers can be divided into external (analysis of external interaction) and internal (analysis of internal structures, departments, management within the object).

"The situation center should, in accordance with the data, ensure:

- 1) analysis of the information received from the monitoring subsystem;
- 2) modeling the development of the situation on the territory of the city, region, state;
- 3) development and adoption of management decisions to prevent the occurrence of negative situations or minimize their consequences." [6].

The situational approach to making the right managerial decision by the manager makes it possible to have a holistic real representation of the object itself and its specific management decision, interaction and functioning from the outside, etc. "Well-organized work of the situation center allows us to prepare and make well-grounded strategically important decisions, to avoid many managerial mistakes in traditional approaches to management, which are mainly based on the principle of own trial and error. Situational centers provide an opportunity to conduct a preliminary analysis of the current situation, monitor the progress of its changes and predict its expected changes. This makes the situational approach more effective, allowing you to avoid, at times, significant losses of resources and time." [7].

3. Situational modeling of the system

Fig 1. Situational modeling of systems. Source: Created by the author

The situation center is an innovative form of systematization of analytical and information activities, accumulation of information and presentation of data, using the latest communicative and technological means.

Situational modeling can be divided according to classification criteria, direction and purpose. (Fig. 1).

Situational display of information is based on situational centers of reflection and their distribution, which gives stability and consistency in the use of information for the correct adoption of managerial decisions.

Simulation of situations can be developed by performing both direct tasks (involving information display and analytics) and inverse tasks (when analyzing the possibility and simulation modeling of data determination).

Analytical situational systems (situational control) is based on the principles of assuming the large existence of states of systems, examples of final decisions are limited, and the final decision is made thanks to the initial data.

Situational centers have a structure that is formed due to the functional orientation and types of support (qualification and personnel, information, technical, innovative, mathematical and computing, philological and linguistic, economic and financial, etc.)

The functionality of the situation center should have three main tools of influence: dynamic modeling of behavioral aspects of the external environment, dynamic modeling of behavioral aspects of the internal environment and interaction, decision-making for a positive joint result.

According to the Order of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine No. 396 dated 23.12.2021 "On the establishment of a working group on the creation and functioning of the situation center in the system of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine" it is determined: to form a working group and establish that the main task is to prepare proposals and information materials on:

- "ways to create a situation center in the system of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine and the Armed Forces of Ukraine;
- assessment and determination of the list of threats that should be responded to with the deployment of a situation center in the system of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine;
- opportunities to respond jointly with the Armed Forces of Ukraine to a certain list of threats;

- possibilities of deployment of a backup situation center and centers on mobile vehicles;

- equipping the situation center with unified software and hardware for information and analytical support of managerial decision-making. [8].

The situation center group must determine the list of possible threats and response methods to prevent negative consequences. The Ministry of Defence of Ukraine can work with the Armed Forces of Ukraine both jointly and separately make decisions.

"Information security is the state of security of the system for transmitting, processing and storing data, which ensures the confidentiality, availability and integrity of data. Information security includes a set of measures that should ensure the protection of data from unauthorized access, use, disclosure, modification or destruction.

"The formation of information cleansing is a long systemic process for the country, and for deep hygienic prevention of the population, it is necessary to understand the purpose and goals, means and prospects of manipulators and disinformers in the digital space. It is possible to identify some actualizations of the process, which will contribute to a more accurate definition of the problem and the formulation of a solution in the future:

- *I know that I don't know anything (the desire to learn, discuss and realize myself, without trying to convince everyone that I am right);*

- *understanding and acknowledging the multi-vector and fragmented nature of the information field (to recognize special fakes of the Ukrainian special services, disseminated deliberately);*

- *comparative analysis with a recognized (untainted) information field (verification of information (fakes) from various information carriers, based on verified and reliable sources);*

- *cleaning up your information field (constant prevention and removal of compromised information channels);*

– *non-proliferation (reaction and answers to painful topics, timely refutations, anti-likes);*

– *investigation of the trail (analysis of emotions, increased vigilance);*

– *anti-Ukrainian sources (open Russian propaganda)". [9].*

Types of information security threats:

- gaining access to classified or confidential data;
- disruption or complete cessation of the computer information system;
- gaining access to the control of the computer information system;
- destruction or distortion of data". [10].

Situational centers are effective means of implementing systems aimed at making managerial decisions on the basis of the information field, which includes: analysis, monitoring, decision-making, implementation and control of the process. "The network should include: the main situation center of Ukraine; Government Situation Center; situational centers of security and defense sector bodies; Situational Centers of Central Executive Bodies". [11].

4. Work of the situation center of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The Main Situation Center at the National Security and Defense Council distributes functions and tasks between the Situation Centers of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine and the Situation Centers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, which closely cooperate in a single direction.

The Situation Center of the Armed Forces of Ukraine is a point of the main directorate, which ensures the implementation of the smooth functioning of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the military leadership of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, designed to collect information and summarize databases that contribute to the analysis, forecasting, modeling of support for managerial decision-making of the activities of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in peacetime, in a special period before the introduction of the legal regime of martial law.

Implementation of Regulations and Laws of Ukraine	Tasks of the Situation Center of the Armed Forces of Ukraine
Implementation and compliance with public policy	
Mobilization and imposition of martial law and implementation of measures	
Awareness of all areas of execution and military command	
Bringing orders and orders to all services, monitoring the implementation	
Elimination of the consequences of emergencies in accordance with the norms and operational documents	
Analysis and monitoring of the real situation for decision-making	
Collecting, processing, inferring, and responding to the state of military operations	
Accumulation and storage of information for constant readiness	
Interaction and interconnection between all spheres of military command	
Information analysis between other military command and control bodies	
Forecasting and Statistical-Comparative Analysis of Events	
Organization of the use of all opportunities of the state potential	

Fig 2. Tasks of the Situation Center of the Armed Forces of Ukraine.

Created by the author at [12]

The Armed Forces of Ukraine have the main tasks that are aimed at implementation, with their own functions and directions:

- modes of daily performance and functioning (consistency and accuracy of the main tasks, monitoring of everyday situations, planning and analysis of the necessary forces for emergencies, support and control of combat readiness);
- combat readiness mode (increased mode) (information and notification of military personnel, enhanced duty and mobilization of forces to eliminate crisis situations, clarification and planning of actions, forecasting and analytics, proposals for effective decision-making, prevention measures and work with the population);
- emergency situation regime (performance of actions of daily performance and operation and high readiness, communication with all military command and control bodies, determination of the degree of risk, format and area of the emergency, response and control, systematic updating of information and taking measures);
- state of emergency (unity and response of all participants in the liquidation of the crisis situation, in the implementation of all regimes).

The composition, structure and tasks of the situation center of the Armed Forces of Ukraine may change depending on the level of threat (crisis) by the decision of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Ukraine (Deputy Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of Ukraine).

5. Difficulties and directions of the work of situational centers. The structural subdivisions of the situation center depend on the complexity and direction of the goals and objectives of the organization:

- large-scale (complex) functioning (strategic level);
- multi-purpose functioning (target level), (specific observation and possible use of information, advanced training of employees, etc.);
- deterministic functioning (risk level), (objective reality and perception);
- situational functioning (multifunctional level);
- stationary operation (at the location);
- collective and individual functioning (level of employee involvement);
- universal functioning (wide level of tasks).

The main situation center in the general system of situational centers of state executive authorities is the center of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine.

An important role in the work of the situation center is the location of the organization and the distribution of functional areas. Typical centers have several work areas that should be interconnected: a hall for meetings, analytical and modeling areas (technical equipment, a separate room), working rooms for analysts, IT experts, operators' rooms (rapid response areas), utility rooms for staff.

Conclusion. Situation center is a system that solves management problems by methods of rapid response of situational management, taking into account the realities and forecasts of the state of the object. The Situation Center is an innovative software and hardware integrated tool aimed at planning and functioning of the innovation and technical base for mutual provision of receiving, accumulating and processing information and the organizational and business process, tools and tools (organization of workplaces for staff, analysts, IT experts and management). The

work of the situation center should work around the clock, in the mode of full readiness to respond to any situation, constantly using new methodologies of work in the mode of daily functioning and in the state of emergency. Today, it is necessary to take into account specialized methods for the development of modern innovation space (social networks, instrumental modeling tools, rapid response technologies, disinformation monitoring, etc.). At this stage, we must morally support our soldiers and the efforts of the state, provide technical, material, programmatic, military capabilities and take a broad step towards victory

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